

THE RELEVANCE OF THE USE OF ELECTRONIC MEDIA FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *In this article we will consider the benefits of using electronic media for teaching foreign languages. In modern society, much attention is paid to the search for new forms, methods, and techniques of teaching. The modern school needs such teaching methods that could not only teach high-quality but also reveal the personality of a person, his creative potential. Also, modern education should teach a person to adapt to modern life, teach him to make decisions quickly and correctly, and actively master situations of social change.*

Keywords: *foreign language, electronic media, ICTs, modern educational technologies, information technologies, teaching foreign languages.*

The system of teaching a foreign language can be effective if it is based on modern methodological approaches. In modern conditions, the use of various technologies, electronic means in teaching foreign languages, affect the acquisition of new language skills in students. The introduction of a new educational technology requires a revision of the existing norms and rules of the organization of the educational process in a modern educational institution, which allows the most effective implementation of certain models of innovative education. Innovative education is considered as a systematic set of educational processes based on the active application of the latest information and organizational and pedagogical technologies with the use of theoretical, practical and pedagogical innovations. The introduction of information technologies contributes to the intensification of the educational process [1].

Currently, the main ideas of all modern educational technologies are as follows:

- * students ' participation in pair work related to oral activities;
- * quickly view text and identify key information;
- * telling entertaining stories;
- * follow various instructions;
- * planning, preparation of an article in a foreign language;
- * writing a story for a specific group or genre [2].

Modern information and communication technologies (ICTs) are able to provide this. It is now easy to record students ' speech using computers or mobile phones, using MP3 players, store it, play it back and share it effortlessly . Teachers can record a video of the students ' paired or group work, then view it, evaluate their work and the work of students, and make adjustments. Students can write blogs effortlessly, providing comments and feedback on written work. ICTs contribute not only to practical work, but also provide students and teachers with theoretical materials: recordings of native speakers for listening, authentic texts on the specialty, business games, etc.[3].

One of the fastest growing means of electronic communication is the Internet. The modern Internet provides a foreign language teacher with virtually inexhaustible information resources, as well as new technical capabilities that can significantly improve the quality of teaching foreign languages. The distinctive characteristics of these resources are authenticity, relevance, information content, the presence of intersubject links, multimedia, etc. Thanks to the new Internet technologies, the teacher can solve individual specific tasks related to the educational process as

efficiently as possible in the shortest possible time with the least expenditure of effort and money [4]. There are a number of reasons why this technology is of great interest and deserves special attention from professionals in the field of teaching foreign languages. The use of the Internet in teaching a foreign language corresponds to the main goal of studying a foreign language in higher education – the formation of communicative competence, providing students with the opportunity to develop communication skills, the ability to inter-cultural interaction, as well as the skills of independent work.

To date, the most universal technical means of training are electronic interactive whiteboards SMART Board. Electronic interactive whiteboards are an effective way to introduce electronic content of educational materials and multimedia materials into the learning process. The lesson material is clearly outlined on the interactive whiteboard screen and aims each student at active and fruitful activity. Pre-prepared thematic texts in English, training and testing exercises, colorful pictures of various types, the material of English-language multimedia discs, audio and video materials serve to introduce or activate the lesson material, repeat or consolidate the lexical units and grammatical structure of the language, control and self-control of knowledge. The interactive whiteboard allows you to work without using a keyboard, "mouse" and computer monitor [5]. All the necessary actions can be performed directly on the screen using a special marker or even a finger. The teacher does not distract from the lesson to perform the necessary manipulations at the computer. This has a positive effect on the quality of the presentation of educational material. Thus, using an interactive whiteboard, you can organize the permanent work of the student in electronic form. This significantly saves time, stimulates the development of mental and creative activity, and involves all students in the group. So, the reasonable use of the almost limitless possibilities of modern technical means in English classes should contribute to the formation of language competencies, the development of creative thinking and, most importantly, the desire for continuous improvement [6].

Conclusion. The question of the use of new information technologies in teaching English is becoming more and more relevant. The use of new information technologies in teaching foreign languages means not only the practical application of modern technical means and technologies, but also the use of new forms and methods of teaching a foreign language and the approach to the learning process as a whole. One of the main tasks of the teacher is to activate the activity of each student, creating a situation for creative activity. It is quite obvious that the use of a computer and multimedia tools helps not only to implement a person-oriented approach to learning, but also to ensure individualization and differentiation, taking into account the level of knowledge of students. A lot depends on the teacher, on his desire to use information technology in a foreign language lesson.

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